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Stylistic Analysis of Suicide Notes

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Abstract:

This article presents a stylistic analysis of authentic suicide notes obtained from various courts in Greater Mumbai. The study aims to identify stylistic patterns and explore the linguistic choices made by individuals in these notes. To protect individuals' identities, all notes have been anonymized. A framework grounded in linguistic and stylistic theories was developed and employed to guide the analysis. Each note was manually examined within this framework to identify distinctive stylistic and linguistic features. The findings indicate that individuals experiencing emotional distress often exhibit particular stylistic characteristics. These insights contribute to a more systematic understanding of suicide notes and may inform future research in this area.

Keywords: Suicide notes, stylistic analysis, style, analytical model.

Introduction:

The study presents the stylistic analysis of suicide notes. A suicide note is a message written by an individual who has committed suicide or who wishes to commit suicide. Suicide adds

emotional and economic problems, including healthcare costs to individuals and society. Every year around eight lakh people commit suicide worldwide. Around 25-30% of people leave suicide notes behind. The Government of India defines the act of intentionally ending one's life as suicide, an unnatural form of death. The reasons behind the act are often disclosed in the suicide notes. In India, common methods of suicide include poisoning, hanging, and self-immolation. Suicide was once considered a criminal act in India, and survivors could be penalized with imprisonment and a fine under Section 309 of the IPC. The Mental Healthcare Act of 2017 decriminalized attempted suicide and repealed the earlier provision. Suicide cases in India are recorded under Section 306 of the Indian Penal Code. Individuals who take their own lives are generally believed to be experiencing severe mental distress and, therefore, should not be subjected to punitive measures. According to data from the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), the suicide rate in India rose by 4.2% in 2022 compared to 2021, increasing from 12 to 12.4 per 100,000 population. The NCRB data also reveals a consistent upward trend in suicide rates, rising from 9.9 per lakh population in 2017 to 12.4 per lakh in 2022.

The present study employs both qualitative and quantitative approaches to analyze forty suicide notes collected from various Sessions Courts in the Greater Mumbai area. Drawing on theories from applied linguistics and stylistics, the analysis identifies linguistic and stylistic features that may serve as parameters for examining authentic suicide notes. The findings of this study can inform future content analysis of such notes.

Aims and Objectives of the Research:

To develop an analytical model based on research theories.

To study suicide notes quantitatively and qualitatively.

To describe the role of stylistics in suicide notes.

To identify the role of style markers in handwritten suicide notes.

Method

A total of forty suicide notes analyzed in this study were collected from Sessions Courts in the Greater Mumbai region. In India, suicide cases are registered under Section 306 of the Indian Penal Code. Judgment copies pertaining to Section 306 were reviewed to identify the presence of suicide notes. Photocopies of these notes were obtained from the courts upon submission of formal applications and supporting affidavits. To maintain confidentiality, all notes were anonymized to protect the identities of the deceased. The study focuses on a linguistic and stylistic analysis of the content of these notes, guided by established theories in linguistics and stylistics.

Literature Review

Adil Jaafar, E., and Abdul-Salam Jasim, H. (2022) analyzed the stylistic and linguistic characteristics of suicide notes posted on Reddit between 2012 and 2020. The findings revealed that the notes commonly featured simple vocabulary and short sentence structures. There was a substantial occurrence of first-person singular pronouns, and among content words, verbs were the most frequently used, followed by nouns, adjectives, and adverbs.

Jasim, H. A., and Jaafar, E. A. (2022) reviewed previous work focusing on content and stylistic analysis of suicide notes. Their work focused on examining suicide notes and online posts through a range of methodologies, showcasing the application of stylistic theories and corpus analysis tools to extract key linguistic and stylistic characteristics.

Sihite, A. D. P. et al. (2023) studied the suicide note of Swedish singer, Per Ohlin and noted some distinguished features. There were positive, negative, and cognitive emotions. They carried out forensic semantic analysis and structural analysis of the suicide note. The note conveyed negative emotional states, and the writer identified with the idea of death, ultimately leading to the act of suicide.

Kanyama, J. K. (2023) carried out a discourse analysis on suicide notes to decide their authenticity. The suicide letters and notes had positive, negative emotions and grammatical inaccuracies.

Br Sitepu, E. F. et al. (2023) conducted a stylistic analysis within a forensic context, highlighting the difficulties associated with understanding and interpreting language. The study centered on forensic stylistics and analyzed a case involving a female student who had authored a suicide note.

Maulida, D. E. et al. (2024) conducted a descriptive-qualitative analysis of the linguistic features found in a suicide note written by a UNNES student, using Prokofyeva's theoretical framework for suicide note language. The researchers categorized and examined the note based on five key linguistic characteristics: clear reasoning, emotional expression, text structure, grammar, and punctuation. The study revealed that all five

features were present in the note; however, the researchers also observed variations in the use of verb tenses throughout the text.

Lubis, E. R. et al. (2024) explored forensic stylistics to find its role in finding deeper meaning in suicide notes and the author's mental state before death. The structure, grammar, punctuation, cultural framework, and vocabulary preferences of suicide notes give a comprehensive view of the author's mental confusion.

Amalia, K. D. et al. (2024) utilized a descriptive qualitative research approach to examine suicide notes sourced from the India Today news website via Google search. Language can meaningfully influence the investigative process by explaining implied meaning.

Siahaan, R. P. (2024) employed a qualitative descriptive approach to analyze the suicide note written by YAP. The researcher tried to explore elements such as logical reasoning, emotional expression, text structure, grammar, and punctuation. The note's structure adheres to a familiar pattern, beginning with an apology, followed by an explanation of the motives behind the suicide, expressions of concern for family members, and concluding with a final request.

Theoretical Framework:

Style is a flexible feature of a language and is related to the motive of communication. Style is a tool for analyzing the language. Dr. Samuel Johnson considered style as manner and as a means of distinguishing an author. He found individual styles to be a repetition of specific manners which can be easily noted. Dr. Johnson was the first to

propose that style has a characteristic aspect. In forensic analysis, identifying an author often relies on the consistent repetition of certain stylistic and linguistic features. Although authors tend to exhibit certain features consistently, human behavior is subject to variation and imitation. Authors often adapt their writing styles and may adopt features from one another, reflecting the flexible nature of stylistic expression. While human behavior and actions tend to remain relatively stable, they can exhibit a degree of variability depending on the individual and the context. The established Style stays with the person. The verbal language style is related to linguistic differences resulting from social, cultural and geographic settings. Factors such as age, gender, race, culture, education, and income influence an individual's verbal style, while written style is shaped by contextual elements such as the situation, audience, and genre.

Written style evolves through a writer's consistent preference for certain forms over others. The choices can show variation within a norm, a choice among acceptable form. For example, twenty – five/ twenty five/ 25. Deviations from the norm may include forms that are considered unacceptable, for example, I might go/ I could go/ I might could go.

In linguistics, synonyms are words that convey the same meaning in different shades or with different stylistic features. Stylistics has used theories from contemporary literary criticism and linguistics.

The pedagogical role of stylistics is connected to the understanding and explanation by readers. Stylistics informs the explanation formed by the readers. Practical stylistics includes close reading of the verbal quality of texts. Stylistics wants iconic equations

between noted linguistic choices, structures and the depiction of meaning. It connects linguistic form and literary meaning. Language cannot be identified as a distinctive object that we can single out and study. Style is the study material of stylistics.

Individual Style

Even among speakers of the same language, stylistic variations can be observed in both speech and writing. Subgroups within a community are often distinguishable by their unique register, jargon, or slang. A register is a socially controlled way of speaking that is apt for a specific professional setting. Individuals exhibit stylistic variation in their idiolect, reflecting the unique linguistic traits of both speakers and writers. Linguistic variation in a person's writing represents their unique idiolect. There can be inter-writer variation, variation between a writer and other members of the same speech community. There is also intra-writer variation, variation within the writer.

Style of Suicide Notes

Every suicide has a different theme and style. Linguistic features like lexical, syntactical and pragmatic can be extracted to measure the style of a note. Apart from these pure linguistic features, extra linguistic features like text structure and layout could also be valuable information in the analysis of suicide notes. The analysis includes linguistic features like parts of speech and lexical frequency and structural features like the number of paragraphs, number of sentences, and sentence length.

Methods of Stylistic Analysis

Stylistic Variations: The analyzer should consider all norms of language behavior in collected samples. The variation in writing is explained using social, geographic and situational norms. The writers show various levels of consciousness in language production.

Description of Style Markers: Specific markers that are highly rare are identified. In each set of writings, the entire variation is analyzed quantitatively.

Qualitative Analysis: The qualitative analysis concentrates on the systematic linguistic depiction of forms. The process follows consideration, depiction, evaluation and outcome. In the process, the style markers are noticed in the writing.

Quantitative Analysis: The linguistic variation recognizes the amount and frequency of systems used by a writer. A pattern is formed with two or more illustrations. In quantitative analysis, determining frequency is simpler because statistical tests show the minimum number of instances required for their valid application.

Analytical Model:

The analytical model is prepared by following the theoretical aspects of stylistic analysis. Every note is manually analyzed using the analytical model to extract the stylistic features. The stylistic analysis includes measurement of connectors, qualifiers, referents, active verbs and passive verbs. The stylistically marked vocabulary is noted. The stylistic and linguistic variations are counted. The style markers are separated. The extra-linguistic features are noted down. The use of loan words or hybrid terms is noted to find out whether

suicide victims have borrowed terms from other languages. Stylistic variations could be social, geographic or situational. Style markers can be identified according to medium, orthography, graphology and punctuation. Extra linguistic features such as the structure of the text, layout and inclusion of postscripts have been considered for the analysis.

Connectors.
Qualifiers.
Referents.
Active Verbs.
Passive Verbs.
Vocabulary.
Hybrid Terms, Borrowed Terms.
Stylistic Variations- Social, Geographic, Situational.
Style Markers- According to Medium, Orthographic, Graphology, Punctuation.
Extra Linguistic Features- Text structure, Layout, Postscript.
Linguistic Variations- Intrapersonal.

Result and Discussion:

i. 97.5% of suicide victims used connectors like and, but, who, that, etc. in their writing to bind utterances together and to show consequences/ reasons for certain things. The higher frequency of conjunctions shows an apologetic personality trait. The use of connectors in the notes is part of a complex structure. The connectors help to form links

between ideas and narrate them. Connectors can indicate spontaneity and difficulty in maintaining decisions. Frequent use of these connectors may suggest that the person is less confident and lacks a sense of authority. According to Weintraub (1989), a high frequency of conjunctions reflects a personality that tends to be apologetic or prone to rationalizing. The conjunctive phrases enable us to figure out the relationship between two sentences. Genuine suicide notes have clear reasoning. The expressions of the emotional state of the author, like fear of living, expression of relief, absence of hope and desire and absence of doubt are observed. Foster (2003) noted that 60% of people convey their love in a suicide note to those whom they leave behind.

ii. The use of qualifiers is made by 70% of suicide victims to enhance the intensity of expressions. Qualifiers include expressions of uncertainty and modifiers that weaken statements. According to Weintraub (1989), the use of qualifiers increases as anxiety increases. Their frequent use shows indecisiveness and lack of commitment. Example - just, a lot, very much.

iii. All suicide notes used referents so that references about things will be explicit, making their percentage 100%. Example - these, this, who, we, it, that.

iv. All suicide notes made use of active verbs. The suicide victims took responsibility for their message and actions. The use of active verbs presents a person as assertive.

v. 35% of suicide victims also used passive verbs in their writing to underline their helplessness. Passive verbs show people as inactive and helpless.

vi. In all notes, the stylistic variations are situational, making their percentage 100%. The suicide victims did not remain consistent in the usage of terms and forms due to the mental stress they experienced at the time of death.

Example – dreams - shattered dreams - horrible dream - dreams crashing down

vii. The style markers are used according to the use of medium, making its percentage 95%. Marathi and Hindi notes have language-specific vocabulary. The writing style can identify many factors, like age, education, social status etc. 37.5% of notes have orthographic style markers like spelling, capitalization, cancellation, overwriting etc. Osgood and Walker (1959) suggested that spelling and punctuation errors in suicide notes may stem from the psychological drive associated with suicidal ideation. They noted that such notes often contain structural issues, including misspellings, punctuation mistakes, and awkward phrasing.

example- LAST GUDBYE TO ALL OF YOU

IAM COMMITTING SUICIDE

D odds

Borrowed Terms- mangalsutra, Aai, baba, bhabi, subzi-roti stall, chawl, sahib, kholi.

Spelling - than(then), torture(tortured), faled, 2 me, 2 liv

Capitalization- MERO CAB, Dead Body, Loyal, Love, DAD,

viii. Of the suicide victims studied, 67.5% wrote a note that was no longer than one page. Ten percent wrote two-page notes, while 5% wrote three-page notes. Another

5% wrote four-page notes, 5% wrote six-page notes, and 5% wrote seven-page notes. Only one individual wrote an eleven-page note, representing 2.5% of the sample. These findings suggest that most suicide victims preferred brief written communication. Jones and Benell (2007) observed that such brevity is often associated with heightened emotional arousal, resulting in shorter and less varied sentence fragments.

ix. 57.5% of suicide victims signed the suicide note, making it authentic and reliable. 42.5% of suicide victims did not sign suicide notes. It may not be a deliberate attempt. The person under mental stress may not be bothered by the formalities of written language.

x. 27.5% of suicide victims wrote notes with indentation whereas 72.5% did not use indentation. The conventions of written language are not followed in stressful moments. 20% of suicide victims mentioned the date in the note. 7.5% of suicide victims wrote with conventional greetings and complimentary close. 2% of suicide victims opted for postscript as the majority thought that they conveyed enough in the note and there was no need for any addition.

xi. 52.5% of suicide victims showed intrapersonal linguistic variations. The suicide victims under emotional stress do not remain consistent in the usage of linguistic forms.

Example- IM-I AM, you-u, I have- I've.

The textual analysis shows that 75% of suicide victims did not use indentation while writing the note. This practice may not be deliberate, but due to emotional load, people may not follow the letter-writing conventions. 62.5% of people signed the note, taking

responsibility for the message, 7.5% of people underlined the signature and 15% put more than one signature. 20% of victims have added date in the suicide note. 5% of people have added a salutation and complementary close in the note. 90% of suicide victims used more space and gaps in letters in writing, which indicates a gap in the thought process. 33% of suicide victims used cancellation of words, overwriting, indicating the emotional load they faced while writing it. 10% of suicide victims used more than one addressee. 5% of people addressed notes to police authorities. 67.5% of suicide victims used one paragraph to write the note.

The stylistically marked phrases and clauses underline the plight and help readers understand the mental pressure and depression the person underwent at the time of suicide. The use of stylistically marked words, nouns and verbs makes readers understand the trauma experienced at that moment. The vocabulary can be specific when emotional content is discussed.

Conclusion

The comprehensive analytical model, incorporating both linguistic and stylistic research theories, significantly aided in the systematic analysis of suicide notes and helped to draw clear conclusions. Each note was manually examined using this model, with findings recorded through both qualitative and quantitative methods. The collected data showed a higher frequency of connectors, conjunctions, qualifiers and referents. The use of active voice was observed in all suicide notes. The notes showed situational stylistic variations. Orthographic style markers like capitalization, cancellation, and overwriting were noted in collected notes. Most of the suicide victims opted for short communication.

Textual analysis exhibited specific features. The intrapersonal linguistic variation is observed in suicide victims.

These recorded observations can serve as a foundation for structured analysis of suicide notes. The conclusions using stylistic analysis can focus on the difficulties of metropolitan people and support the government in recommending different policies.

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